
Occultism and Disease Healing in Lani Tribe – Papua

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Abstract

In general, the Papuan people, specifically the Lani people, cannot be separated from powerful tribal religious beliefs. The belief includes belief in the spirits of the dead, belief in objects that have authority and power overall life. It is continued to be taught from generation to generation to new generations in the scope of informal Education to inherit the values of belief and apply them in the practice of everyday life. As stated by Wach (2019), understanding of religion is not drawn from “revelation” from the outside world but is lifted from concrete experiences around religion from the past (history) as well as from current events. The meaning of the definition of religion, according to sociology, is a type of social system created by its adherents who pivot on non-empirical forces that they believe in and use to achieve salvation for themselves and society at large. The life of the Lani people before the advent of the Gospel was indeed a life filled with fear, and there was no freedom because everywhere there were enemies who were ready to stand in front of them to kill their lives either directly or indirectly by using the powers of darkness.

1. Introduction

In today's world, especially in the life of believers (Christians), most of them claim to be followers of Christ, but at certain times, they still believe in other powers that are considered to have authority around them. The forces of darkness are thought to be contained in particular sacred objects that can control the life of the Lani tribe in Konda Tolikara- Papua, Indonesia. Theologically, because people believe all of that so that the spirits of darkness govern their lives and daily activities, and they worship the powers of those spirits. They continue to worship idols because they think there is salvation, power, and there is science in the idols.

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The belief of the Lani people, before the Gospel came, was to live and believe in the powers of darkness as rulers in mountains, rocks, forests, land, and certain places that are considered to have supernatural powers and supernatural powers. Particular objects are called "sacred objects", which they always keep in a specific location and are not commonly known by everyone. As a result of all kinds of objects considered sacred, birds and animals became evil in front of the Lani people; finally, they believed that there was an attraction on top of that majestic mountain like a magnet. In connection with this paper, the researcher describes a theoretical study and a descriptive explanation related to the occult and healing diseases practised by the Lani-Papuan tribe.

2. Materials and Methods

This paper applied the literature review technique to present some literature issues related to the topic. To be specified, this paper involves scoping literature review technique. As implied by its name, it identifies the scope of coverage of a body of literature on a given topic. It has been noted that "scoping reviews are useful for examining emerging evidence when it is still unclear what other, more specific questions can be posed and valuably addressed by a more precise systematic review." The main difference between systematic and scoping types of a literature review is that a systematic literature review is conducted to find answers to more specific research questions, whereas scoping literature review is conducted to explore more general research questions.

3. Results and Discussions

3.1 Occult Practice

Occult derived from the word "occult", which means "dark", and "ism", which means "teaching" or "understanding" about dark things. At the same time, the word "unseen" means "invisible", hidden and difficult for people to know. Occult science is the study of all actions, unreal conditions such as the secrets of nature, strange powers - strange or unreasonable human beings. Occultism is an unquestioning belief in demons, spirits of the dead, gods, demons, evil spirits, ancestral stories that contain promises, incantations, amulets, customs that support elements of shaman belief—Fortune tellers, sorcerers, idols, ancestral graves, etc. (Spence, 2003). Occult practice is the existence of an understanding or belief in the Power and Power of other objects that deny or do not believe in the Power of God.

3.2 Disease Healing

Healing disease or cure is taken from the Greek "therapeu" or therapy. Healing or therapy is an attempt to restore the health of sick people; disease treatment or disease treatment. The Lani tribe believes that if someone is sick, they take the ill family member to a particular person who can provide healing by cutting one or several pigs and splitting the pig's stomach and then examining the inside of the pig's belly where the disease is and the type of illness of the sick person.

After that, they asked the idols above and below. The idol above is called "*Erilek*" (no hair), and the idol below is called "*Nalugwe*". The person who asks for help from the idol is particular. After examining the pork belly, they began to burn the pork (*Wam*) on the edge of the *honai* (the name of a mountain person's house), then only men joined in eating.

Certain people carry out the occult practice of treating the sick by determining the type of disease. The location of the disease in the human body through belief in the powers of idols dramatically affects the growth of the faith of the members of the Jama'at, even sometimes the members of the

congregation themselves ask the shaman so that the disease can be cured or to find out the cause of his illness. They do not go to the hospital first for treatment while praying. Or vice versa, they go to the hospital but have not experienced a final recovery, call a shaman to give treatment by splitting the pig's stomach.

3.3 Occultism according to the Old Testament

Some verses in the old testament that speak about occultism are presented as follows. First, it is written in Genesis 3:1, about the serpent is a creature that appeared as a person and spoke with Eve. Next, in the book of Job 1:6; 2:1, it is told about satan who can join the children and come before God. The same as in Job 1:7-12; 2:2-7, The Lord God held an interview with Satan about Job's righteousness, while in Job 1:7-8; 2:2-3, there was a pronoun 'you' that referred for demons, as written "where have *you* come from". After that, in 1 Chronicles 21:1, it is written that the satan rises against the Israelites, and in the book of Zachariah 3:1-2, it shows that the satan is standing at his right hand the priest Joshua to accuse him.

If the satan does not defeat humans by deceiving the human mind, then he will also try to destroy the human body. As snakes can cleverly deceive with their lies, humans are unaware that they are killing themselves. If humans are happy with his deception, the satan will attack the human body. He lost the property that supported his life, including livestock and wealth. And what Job felt was an awful disease. His friends just sat quietly for a week, watching Job's terrible suffering. Even his wife could not bear to see Job's temptations, so she said: "Curse your God, and Job will die." This is because Satan attacked Job's body ultimately as well as everything related to it (Fleming, 1994).

In the Torah, in the Old Testament (Genesis 3), the punishment for disobedience as shown by the enemy does not seem cruel. Therefore, Eve could consider ignoring God's will rather than Satan's will. Once man treats God's Word like that, the door of the satan's deception opens wide. Satan allowed Eve to judge the tree of the knowledge of good and evil, apart from God's written and spoken Word (Genesis 2:7).

Since Adam and Eve were cast out of the garden of Eden and the world's population has increased. (Genesis 6:1-13). God punishes humans through the Flood because humans are increasingly opening their hearts to the evil conspiracy of the satan to leave God's plan. Humans are increasingly proliferating but living in sin. They trust supernatural powers, which are considered more helpful in surviving every life; this is nothing but occult practice (Zefit, 2013). The only thing in the New Testament that mentions about Job is in James 5:11, "...we count as blessed those who have persevered. You have heard of Job's perseverance and have seen what the Lord finally brought about. The Lord is full of compassion and mercy". This verse shows that Satan meant for Job not to persevere and give up. Job was indeed a person who lacked patience with himself and his friends who criticized him, but he never lost his faith in God. Even though he didn't understand what God was doing, Job knew he could trust God, and God would defend him until he died. In general, as if persevering, they can't sit too long and wait for something to be done.

Diligence is also a sign of distrust. If you are restless and worried about doing something, it means that humans are not trusting God in their work. Humans will all be like God. Faith and perseverance will go together if we believe in God, then we will wait for him to fulfil His promises. We have an impatient nature, but the Holy Spirit can give patience as a human trait born again. When humans meet a believer who is easily angered and impatient in carrying out God's mandate in this world, and when we believe that the person is walking in the spirit but is more obedient to the works of the flesh.

The origin of the satan can be seen in the old Testament as follows. First, satan came from a holy Angel (Ezekiel 28:1-19). The angels themselves were created by God (Nehemiah 9:6), and the angel who

finally became the satan fallen because it was dissatisfied with his God-given position (Isaiah 14:13-14).

Related to what has been presented, Richardson (1969) stated that perhaps, God created them only after the creation of the heavens and before He created the earth; for according to Job 38:4-7, "all the children of God shouted for joy" when God laid the foundation of the world. While the number of angels is not mentioned in the Bible, we are told their number is enormous (Daniel 7:10; Matthew 26:53; Hebrews 12:22). It drives us to believe that the satan is a creature that exists on this earth.

3.4. The occult according to the New Testament

Hitchcock (1994) argues that the Bible provides complete data about the satan or demons, not just speculation on what humans can see. He adds support for Bible verses: Satan is a real spirit creature (1 Chronicles 21:1; Job 1:6-12; Zechariah 3:1-2; 1 Peter 5:8,9), Satan likes to sow seeds that evil (Matthew 13:39), the satan becomes the enemy of the believer (1 Peter 5:8,9); The satan is called Baalzebul, the prince of demons (Matthew 10:25), the satan is called Belial (II Corinthians 6:15). It means the one who devours is unlucky; Satan is called the master of darkness (Ephesians 6:12); he is called unclean (Matthew 12:43); he is called the tempter or tempter (Matthew 4:3); he is called the evil one (Matthew 13:19).

From the emphasis of the Bible verses, it is known that the satan does exist. Even though our physical eyes do not see him because he is invisible, there are many different interpretations. One of the reasons for knowing the Bible is because the Word of God will enable God's people to resist the powers of darkness, as stated by Johnstone (1998) that with the weapon of God's Word, we can cast out and destroy all the powers and works of satan. The magical object against demons is a weapon without a spirit that can give Power and Power (Habakkuk 2:18, 19). Fight the satan by using the Word of God just as Jesus did.

It is clear that if we do not know the contents of the Bible, we can quickly be taken captive by the satan with his various tricks. The satan drives the practice of occultism (occult sciences), and one of the factors that cause the congregation to fall into this practice is the lack of knowledge of the members of the community about the influence of the Power of the satan itself.

Bell (2007), regarding the understanding of the satan, states that "as God's revelation the Bible provides complete data about the satan or demons, not just speculation on what humans can see. From the biblical explanation above, it can be understood that the satan does exist even though our physical eyes do not see it. Because it is invisible, there are many different interpretations of the satan and his existence.

According to Russell (1987), satan is a personal being, they are created as individuals and are described as intelligent beings, have a will, can decide things, take action, plan tactics, and achieve victory. The New Testament tells us a lot about Satan's activities and God's reaction to them. The satan's tactics gather demons from all corners of the world to hinder and, if possible, thwart the purpose of Christ coming into the world. When the Lord Jesus began His ministry for many people, in front of many people possessed by demons. It seems that his ability to go there is always someone happy to beg for release, and there is also someone who openly challenges His Power. A verse in the book of Mathew states that *news about Him (Jesus) spread all over Syria, and people brought to him all who were ill with various diseases, those suffering severe pain, the demon-possessed, those having seizures, and the paralyzed; and he healed them* (Matthew 4:24).

If we examine properly, these verses will show that demon possession differs from common diseases. In many cases, it is said that Jesus healed diseases and cast out demons. There are remarkable similarities and some symptoms, but we must distinguish these two things carefully.

Some people, besides being possessed, do not necessarily always suffer from illness (Simundson, 1982)

After Christ returned to Heaven and the gospel message continues to spread throughout the world, Christ's followers have been given the mandate to cast out the demonic powers that constantly interfere with human life (Mark 16:17). Three battles determine the pattern of Satan's resistance are shown as follows. First, in the age of evangelism. Here, Jesus was still walking to serve with His disciples. From time immemorial, a man named Simon has done magic in his city and amazed Samaria and pretended to be a significant person (Acts 8:9). Second, a person who likes things that are not seen and evil spirits offers money to buy the Power possessed by the apostles to benefit himself. Peter rebuked the man harshly and stated that the result of trying to confuse the things of God with the things of Satan was because God did not I can cooperate with the satan. Third, after the Apostles Paul and Barnabas departed on their first evangelistic journey, they faced Satan's opposition: "There (at Paphos) they met a Jew named Baryesus who hindered them and tried to turn away from their faith in Jesus (Acts 13:6-8). Paul rebuked the expert harshly and prophesied that sudden blindness would strike the sorcerer.

Another weakness after being used by the satan as an instrument of oppression, but here the problem is quite the opposite; blindness is used to punish the powers of darkness. The sorcerer, whom Paul called "son of the satan", could not stand the power of God. Another ridiculous incident in the city of Ephesus was a father with seven sons, possibly wandering Jews, practising exorcism with incantations. Also, some Jewish chants were walking around in the land, trying to invoke the name of the Lord Jesus on those who were possessed by an evil spirit by shouting, "I swear to us in the name of Jesus which Paul gave. But the evil spirit answered: "Jesus, I know and Paul I know, but who are you? (Acts 19:13 - 15). And the man who was possessed by the evil spirit hit and overpowered them all and defeated him so that they fled from the house with injuries (Cf. Sweet & Viola, 2010).

3.5 Satan's Goals

The satan's goals are to disturb human mind, human body, and human will. When Satan wanted to influence Adam and Eve into sin, he began attacking the first woman's first thoughts. "But I fear that your minds will be led astray from your true loyalty to Christ, just as the serpent deceived Eve with her cunning." (II Corinthians 11:2). The human mind is part of the image of God because, through thoughts, God communicates and reveals His will to us. Unfortunately, some Christians downplay the importance of the mind in that the Bible emphasizes the importance of the renewed human sense.

The book of Colossians states "*Do not lie to each other, since you have taken off your old self with its practices and have put on the new self, which is being renewed in knowledge in the image of its Creator*" (Colossians 3:9-10). Science has discovered many amazing things about the human mind in this day and age. Like a computer, the human mind can store facts, impressions, and even feelings that can resurface in the future. The human mind can reach the past through memory or end through the imagination of human emotions and desires. As a man thinks in himself, so shall he be (Proverbs 23:7).

Next, the satan try to broke human body. If the satan cannot defeat humans by deceiving their minds, he will destroy the human body. As a snake, he fooled a child until the child entered the oak in water and fire. (Matthew 17:14-18). There is no exception here, and Satan wants to attack and destroy the temple of God (Warren W. Wiersbe, 1992: 39).

Finally, satan always has a goal of controlling our wills and then controlling them. Maybe he started by deceiving the mind as he did with Eve or attacking the body as he did with Job, but in the end, it is through trying that he can finally master the human will. But in the case of David, the satan did not go through the mind and body but directly attacked David's choice. In the end, the satan experienced victory. David's mind was not deceived, but his eyes opened wide when he defied God.

David did not suffer physically. On the contrary, his kingdom was victorious. He has won several battles, so he enjoys immense popularity and success.

It is a lesson for Christians not to underestimate the role of the will in the lives of Christians wherever we are in a comprehensive environment. Many believers have religious knowledge that satisfies their minds but never changes their pattern of life. They can discuss the Bible and even argue excitedly about its contents, but when they practice the Word, they always experience failure in their lives. Other Christians have emotional religions. If they are not in good emotions, they often feel that God has far left our inner man who is wholly dedicated to Him: their minds, their steadfast hearts, make Christians move forward in the process of solid faith and willpower. Obedient to Jesus Christ. Our obedience must be based on knowledge and motivated by a heart filled with the warmth of love for our fellow human beings.

Fundamentally, life in Christ is a matter of will. We must love God with all our heart (emotions) and with all our mind (intellectual) and strength (choice). The Holy Spirit wants to rule the mind with the Word, stir the heart with holy and righteous feelings and strengthen the will to do God's will.

Satan's Purpose

The main purpose of satan is to blind human so they cannot see God's will. God's will comes from God himself, which is a very personal matter. God has an intimate understanding of each of His people, all the food they need and their names even down to their nature or character. God wants every human being to know His will. "The God of our fathers appointed you to know his will" (Acts 22:14). God also desires that as humans, we can understand His will: "Therefore do not be foolish, but seek to understand the will of God in your daily life (Ephesians 5:17).

God wants an understanding of His will to fill and control us as His created people. God's will is not an obligation that must be carried out but something that pleases the heart. Therefore every Christian should be pleased with God's will. "My food is to do the will of him who sent me and to finish his work" (Ephesians 4:34). If Satan succeeds in making man blind to God's will, he will rob the man of all the glorious blessings God has planned for man's life. This means that humans will make bad decisions by engaging in sinful activities. It is a sinful and wretched life if humans influence other people to do bad things (false). In his ministry, the author has seen and witnessed the tragic consequences of living outside the will of God.

Next, satan requires humans to not depending on God. Humans are creature whose life depends on something else. A human must rely on God (Acts 17:28) and turn on His servants to keep alive. The essence of sin is the effort not to become independent (independent) on God, placing ourselves as creators and not creations (Romans 1:25). It is this sin that makes us believe in Satan's lie, "*You will become like God*", if Satan deceives humans into acting and thinking in dependence on God, then he can control the human will and life. Maybe humans think that other humans act freely, in which case feelings are just a trick.

The actions or actions of humans are under the control of the rulers of this world. As we studied in the previous sections, God's will is an essential thing in the life of a believer. As an impostor, Satan tries to make people ignore God's will. When Satan talks to people about God, he is lying. But when he talks to God about man, he often seems to be telling the truth, he is an accuser against man because even the satan has no way to enter the kingdom of God, but even before the Throne of God there, he reminds God about the condition of His saints. We need to know this charge because we can feel it in our conscience.

Believers must distinguish between Satan's accusations and the rebuke of the Holy Spirit. Guilt and shame are good when they come from the Spirit of God. If we listen to the satan's voice, the satan's

voice only leads us to deep regret. But if God's Spirit rebukes you, He uses God's Word in love and brings you back into fellowship with the Father.

But when Satan accuses one, he is using one's sin, trying to make one feel helpless and hopeless. Judas listened to the satan and went to sell Jesus and then died by killing himself. The satan influenced Peter, so he was afraid and immediately denied Jesus, but after Peter saw the face of Jesus, he wept and immediately returned to fellowship with Christ. When you listen to the satan's accusations (which seem genuine), you can open yourself up and ask earnestly for God to reveal His will.

Satan's Weapon

Satan's weapons, based on bible explanation, are as follows. First, lie; it is shown when satan came to Eve as a serpent, a cunning impostor, that great dragon called the satan or Satan who misled all humankind in this world. (Revelation 12:9). In him, there is no truth because he is a liar in the world (John 8:44). Believers must pay attention to the steps of Satan to deceive Eve (women) so that she believes in her lies. Women have doubted God's Word, "of course, God has said, he does not deny that God has said: he only questions whether God has spoken.

Sometimes believers misunderstand God's words, "the expression is Satan's suggestion, it should be noted that by this Satan's suggestion, he also intends to doubt God's goodness. Says the satan "if God loves his people, surely he will not hide anything", Satan used the same way when tempting the Lord Jesus in the desert since two thousand years ago. He said, "If you are the Son of God, why are you hungry?"

This satan's statement is a small step from doubting the denial of God's Word. Of course, Adam and Eve had never seen death. Everything they need to stay alive is in God's Word. The Word of God is all they need. If Eve had not listened to Satan, who doubted God's Word, perhaps she would not have fallen into the trap of denial. He replaces his lies. "You will become like God"! Adam and Eve had been created in God's image, but Satan tempted them with something more significant, to be like God.

Second is suffering. Satan wants to control the circumstances around the body so that believers experience suffering. He tried to touch the body and create suffering, as is apparent in the story of Job: he lost his children, his wife, friends and neighbours and wealth. Then Satan attacked Job's personality with an awful disease. When Job looked around him, the situation was harrowing. When he saw himself, he suffered even more. And when he looked up, it seemed that God had abandoned him, even though Job put his faith in God and respected him until the end of time.

It is important to remember that God is always in control of circumstances. Satan could not attack Job if God did not allow it. Satan could not attack Job's person if God did not qualify. This reminds us of what the Lord Jesus said to Peter: "Simon, Simon, behold the satan has demanded to sift you like wheat, but I have prayed for you that your faith may not fail. And when you are converted, strengthen your brethren" (Luke 22:31-32).

In practice, Satan cannot touch God's children without His permission. This truth strengthens us to know that when suffering befalls us, God allows and fully controls the situation. God has no control over how to respond to the natural suffering we experience because of the human condition. For example, we cannot prevent our bodies from deteriorating when we get older. We can experience illness and accidents, and loved ones can abandon us. The things mentioned above happen because of human weakness in a cursed world. We can't blame the satan for that. All creatures groan under the weight of sin, and so do Christians (Romans 8:18-23).

Third, Pride. When Satan suggested counting his people, David felt it was necessary. He has recorded several of David's victories in battle, including capturing the crown of his enemy, which was very beautiful and expensive. David won many matches, but he lost battles because Satan used this victory to inflate David's selfishness and lure David against God.

According to II Corinthians 7:1, believers should not get involved with any physical or spiritual sin they do not feel guilty about because they have not committed any physical or spiritual sin in themselves. They commit physical or spiritual sins such as adultery, greed and others. Don't judge others because they may be spiritually guilty. The prodigal son in Luke 15 sinned physically, but the proud and jealous firstborn was guilty spiritually.

People rarely highlight the spirituality of David, who counted his people to 70,000 perish. However, the sin of adultery is widely discussed, even though only 4 (four) people died as a result of that sin. Today the ChurchChurch is very quick to judge and punish those who fall into physical sin but does not immediately judge and punish those who fall into spiritual sin by not presently evaluating and disciplining church members (especially for church servants) who commit spiritual sins such as pride, and stiff neck in the servant system nan. To a particular degree, pride sinks into each of Satan's temptations, "You will become like God" was the offer he made to Eve. Job heard the criticism of his friends, and he wanted to know why God did not defend him. Even the Lord Jesus tempted Satan with the attraction of pride.

Next, Satan's weapon is indictment. The Apostle Paul faced a situation of accusation in the Corinthian ChurchChurch when a member of the ChurchChurch fell into sin and refused to repent or do what was suitable for God and the ChurchChurch. In I Corinthians 5, Paul told the ChurchChurch to discipline the person. Still, he ignored Paul's advice, so Paul wrote in his letter to the Corinthians that: "For such a person the rebuke of most of you is sufficient" (2 Corinthians 2:6). At first, when sin smelled, the Corinthians were overjoyed and refused to act. Paul's letter surprised them, but they went to the other extreme. They worked too harshly on the person against it to not forgive him. That's why Paul had to guide them. Excessive guilt and sadness only lead to depression, despair and defeat. Sometimes we even try to kill ourselves to escape from the bonds of Satan (sin), so what is our defence against Satan's accusations? (Wiersbe, 1992).

Occult Practices of Healing Diseases for the Lani Tribe community

Unger (1994) states that Satan as a person is expressed through several aspects of actions or actions. – actions that are either directly or indirectly. For people who are sick, he struggles with being free from the disease he is suffering from. Liberation of the sick is the liberation that has become a reality in Christ and can become a reality believed for him. What is meant here by "liberation" is not in the first place liberation from the disease in the "psychosomatic" sense. Freedom, even amid the severe suffering that the sick person is still carrying with all the involvement thereof, can become a reality in his belief. In Jesus Christ, who is Lord and Saviour, even if the suffering is still ongoing, people experience their pain."

Various definitions are given to the work of a doctor. Still, the purpose of medical care is to restore the health of the sick person being treated to participate again in everyday life with other people in society. And the ChurchChurch, in this case, can join in providing pastoral care so that through the pain that he suffers but he finds a way to God. In other words, he can trust God that God will bless the doctor and the various treatments he undergoes to recover from all problems. The pain he was experiencing.

The believer's liberation and his peace with God can affect healing in a psychosomatic sense. We need to admit that in certain situations, illness can be a form of suffering from suffering. Still, the actual suffering of the sick person is no disease in the psychosomatic sense. A sick person's natural stress or grief lies within them in his relationship with God.

Thurnesyen, in his commentary on the letter of James, notes beautiful words by saying that "the sick is he in whom we see, how we are all before God, as children of sin and therefore also children of death. But Jesus Christ, the Son of God, came into the world to save sinners experiencing death. With

these weak and suffering people, he wants to live together. So precisely, the disease is the right place to learn to understand what we find challenging to understand. If we are healthy, it signifies that this is the work of God: "He is weak and suffering".

Suffering from an illness may be part of a memory or discovering a more profound reality. What he had forgotten or had not thought about at all was that the whole relationship with God was wrong, which undermined his acceptance of his life (Abrams, 1999). All that we say makes pastoral ministry difficult, creating tension – tension, sometimes objections. It should be noted that sick people do not always struggle with questions about God and their relationship with him. Sick people usually work with themselves in this we usually understand in life. Church must know all this with care so that the myth does not deceive her that the sick want salvation more than the healthy. It may well happen that the Shepherd in so far as this lies in his ability should endeavour to raise the question of God in the hearts of the sick he serves so that in this way, his egocentrism may be destroyed. And whenever a sick person is tempted to use the Gospel of Jesus Christ as a therapy or a healing tool, they must oppose it and lead the patient to a more profound deliverance that truly brings peace to the sick person.

Of course, as a shepherd, he must gather together with the sick he serves for his bodily healing. But the struggle he must not do is apart from the primary purpose of his ministry. And when giving physical healing to a patient, it must be seen in the light of God's Word and all these things will be added to him (Matthew 6:33).

Pastoral ministry is sometimes misinterpreted because some think that pastoral care for church members is only said about "only spiritual matters". This prejudice is not actually because the pastor and congregation members can talk about many issues that concern the life and various problems of members of the congregation. Therefore, in pastoral care, the pastor or pastor must learn to wait patiently because sick people often unknowingly hinder the pastor in his efforts to direct the patient to focus his whole life on the Power and love of God.

In difficult situations where the pastor often meets with the sick he serves, the phrase "preaching the Word of God cannot be used, what is needed in people's situations like this is to have a calm conversation, which is not too fast, which we should preach several times as a follow-up. Service to the sick is a very time-consuming job.

And also, the powers of darkness are thought to be contained in particular sacred objects that can control the life of the Lani tribe in Konda Tolikara. Because people believe all of that so that the spirits of darkness possess their lives and daily activities, and they worship the powers of those spirits. They continue to worship idols because they think there are: Salvation, there is Power, and there is Education (knowledge).

As a result of all kinds of objects that are considered sacred, birds and other animals become evil in front of the Lani people. finally they believe that the top of the majestic mountain has an attraction like a magnet that makes the Lani people say, "kugi Bilek, put pagamendek, yogo nagatik, wam lambo wangangwi, kandali wangangwi, wandin lambu wangangwi cemuk kanggotio jimuk bo pimogo nago work.

The challenge of the Bible in dealing with occult practices has not yet received serious attention from all regions, especially in the Konda area. When they face suffering, for example, sick and very slow to recover, they immediately look for ways to get healing from a shaman or, according to local customs, heal the sick people get well soon.

The Lani people believe this in the Konda area because if someone is sick, they take their ill family member to a particular person who can provide healing by cutting one or several pigs and splitting the pig's stomach and then examining the inside of the pig's belly where the disease is. And the type of illness of the sick person.

After that, they asked the idols above and below. The idol above is called "Erilek" (no hair), and the idol below is called "Nalugwe". The person who asks for help from the idol is confident. After examining the pork belly, they began to burn the pork (Wam) on the edge of the honai (the name of a mountain person's house), then only men joined in eating.

Certain people carry out the occult practice of treating the sick by determining the type of disease. The location of the disease in the human body through belief in the powers of idols dramatically affects the growth of the faith of the congregation members, even sometimes the members of the congregation themselves ask the shaman so that the disease can be cured or to find out the cause of the illness he is experiencing. They do not go to the hospital for treatment while praying.

4. Conclusion

It often happens among Christians who still emphasize the existence of beliefs in the occult in everyday life, both personally and as a family. For example, when they face suffering caused by belief in supernatural powers, they finally immediately flee to shamans as a guarantee of healing for the disease they are suffering, but what appears is the mere belief which ultimately makes sick people believe in the teachings of that moment and they trust and obey.

This happens a lot in the life of Christians but in particular in the lives of all members of the congregation (Church) who always believe in supernatural powers when they are experiencing suffering, especially when they experience pain, both pain due to work accidents, but also bother due to the presence of a view among the society that the pain is the result of the actions of other people who are jealous by using various means.

It is clear that if we do not know the contents of the Bible, we can quickly be taken captive by the devil with his various tricks. The devil drives the practice of occultism (occult sciences), and one of the factors that cause the congregation to fall into this practice is the lack of knowledge of the members of the community about the influence of the Power of the devil itself.

The challenge of the Bible in dealing with occult practices has not received widespread severe attention from all regions, especially in the Konda area. When they face suffering, for example, sick and very slow to recover, they immediately look for ways to get healing from shamans or according to local customs so that they can be healed. sick people get well soon

The believer's liberation and his peace with God can affect healing in a psychosomatic sense. We need to admit that illness can be a form of suffering in certain situations, but the actual suffering of the sick person is not a disease in the psychosomatic sense. A sick person's natural stress or grief lies within them in his relationship with God.

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